

IDIOMS, PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS AND FORMULAIC EXPRESSIONS

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ABSTRACT

Idiom is a phrase or expression whose total meaning differs from the meaning of the individual words. For example, to blow one's top (get angry) and behind the eight ball (in trouble) are English- language idioms. Idioms come from language and generally cannot be translated literally. Foreign language speakers must learn them just as they would learn vocabulary words. This article defines idioms, phraseological units and formulaic expressions. Moreover, usage of them and examples were given in this paper.

Nowadays English is worth not just knowing, but it is worth really knowing. There is a great importance to understand up-to-date English. English is the chief language of international business and academic conferences, and the leading language of international tourism. English is the main language of popular music, advertising, home computers and video games. Most of the scientific, technological and academic information in the world is expressed in English. International communication expands very fast. The English language becomes the means of international communication, the language of trade, education, politics, and economics. People have to communicate with each other. It is very important for them to understand foreigners and be understood by them. In this case the English language comes to be one but very serious problem. A word comes to be a very powerful means

of communication but also can be a cause of a great misunderstanding if it is not clearly understood by one of the speakers.

Idioms come to be a very numerous part of English. Idioms cover a lot of drawbacks of the English language and it is one-third part of the colloquial speech. The object of the work is the process of using phraseological units and idioms. The subject of the work is phraseological idioms and units in the English language. The hypothesis of the work is as following: if we develop awareness of using idiomatic sentences, we are sure to bring them closer to the authentically sounding speech. The objective of the work is an attempt to study the aspects of idioms, the cases of their usage and to analyze the frequency of idioms usage referring to English and Russian.

To achieve the set aim we determine the following tasks:

1. to classify idioms;
2. to study the problem of the translation of idioms;
3. to understand the aim of the modern usage of idioms;
4. to distinguish different kinds of idioms;
5. to analyze the frequency of idioms' usage referring to English and Russian.

For gaining the mentioned aim we used the following methods:

1. description;
2. observation;
3. critical study of scientific literature and fiction;
4. comparison and contrast.

Scientific novelty is concluded in the comparison of two languages, belonging to different language families.

Theoretical value consists in revealing the fact that idioms can't and mustn't be translated directly as such a branch of language as idioms are inseparably connected with nation's mentality and mode of life. The practical value consists in the fact that the present work is a valuable manual for specialists concerned with teaching English and for those who study English and can be used as a teaching guide for stirring up idiomatic sentences. The results of the investigation are aimed at raising the quality of translations and preventing mistakes in comprehension. Structurally the presented work consists of: introduction, two parts, conclusion, and bibliography. The introduction reveals the

general survey of the whole work and determines idioms as an essential part of the general vocabulary.

A.V. Koonin classified phraseological units according to the way they are formed. He pointed out primary and secondary ways of forming phraseological units.

Primary ways of forming phraseological units are those when a unit is formed on the basis of a free word-group:

a) Most productive in Modern English is the formation of phraseological units by means of transferring the meaning of terminological word-groups, e.g. in cosmic technique we can point out the following phrases: «launching pad» in its terminological meaning is «стартовая площадка», in its transferred meaning - «отправной пункт», «to link up» - «стыковать космические корабли» in its transformed meaning it means - «знакомиться». A large group of phraseological units was formed from free word groups by transforming their meaning, e.g. «granny farm» - «пансионат для престарелых», «Trojan horse» - «компьютерная программа»;

-Phraseological units can be formed by means of alliteration, e.g. «a sad sack» - «несчастный случай», «culture vulture» - «человек, увлекающийся культурой», «fudge and nudge» - «уклончивость».

-They can be formed by means of expressiveness, especially it is characteristic for forming interjections, e.g. «My aunt!)), «Hear, hear!» etc

-They can be formed by means of distorting a word group, e.g. «odds and ends» was formed from «odd ends»;

-They can be formed by using archaisms, e.g. «in brown study» means «in gloomy meditation» where both components preserve their archaic meanings,

-They can be formed by using a sentence in a different sphere of life, e.g. «that cock won't fight» can be used as a free word-group when it is used in sports (cock fighting), it becomes a phraseological unit when it is used in everyday life, because it is used metaphorically;

Stock of words of the language
According to the Academician V. V. Vinogradov's classification phraseological units may be classified into three groups: phraseological fusions, phraseological unities and phraseological collocations. Phraseological fusions are completely non - motivated word - groups, such as heavy father - "serious or solemn part in a theatrical play", kick the bucket - "die"; and the like. The meaning of the components has no connection whatsoever, at least synchronically, with the meaning of the whole group. Idiomaticity is, as a rule, combined with complete stability of the lexical components and the grammatical structure of the fusion. Phraseological fusions are called "traditional", "set expression with fixed nomination", "combinations", "set expression" in works of other researchers. Phraseological unities are partially non - motivated as their meaning can usually be perceived through the metaphoric meaning of the whole phraseological unit. For example, to show one' s teeth, to wash one' s dirty linen in public if interpreted as semantically motivated through the combined lexical meaning of the component words would naturally lead one to understand these in their literal meaning. The metaphoric

meaning of the whole unit, however, readily suggests "take a threatening tone" or "show an intention to injure" for show one's teeth and "discuss or make public one's quarrels" for wash one's dirty linen in public. Phraseological unities are as a rule marked by a high degree of stability of the lexical components.

Phraseological collocations are motivated but they are made up of words possessing specific lexical valence which accounts for a certain degree of stability in such word - groups. In phraseological collocations variability of member - words is strictly limited. For instance, bear a grudge May be changed into bear malice, but not into bear a fancy or liking. We can say take a liking (fancy) but not take hatred (disgust). These habitual collocations tend to become kind of cliché where the meaning of member - words is to some extent dominated by the meaning of the whole group. Due to this, phraseological collocations are felt as possessing a certain degree of semantic inseparability. In classification of phraseological units according to their structure there are two groups of idioms: nominal a black sheep (of the family) [shame of the family], and verbal to take risks (to risk) as I've already told you. There are more verbal idioms, approximately 65 percent, than nominal ones. In both groups there turns out to be too many idioms, therefore such way is difficult for remembering.

According to academician V. V. Vinogradov's classification there are three groups of idioms. The problem is the same as in the previous case. It's not easy to remember all of these phraseological units.

To sum up, in this course paper there was conducted analysis of idiomatic and stable expressions denoting the subject "information" in the English and Ukrainian languages. This niche of language is of great interest since idiomatic and stable phrases have interesting meanings applied in varied situations. Whilst, the majority of native language speakers can not always

know the origin of idioms they use, though as long as they utilize them in every day communication, they know its meaning and feel where it is appropriate to use this or that idiom. Undoubtedly, the correct usage of English and Ukrainian idioms is finesse, which makes the language of the speaker more vivid and exciting.

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